

A Continuous Adjoint Framework for Vehicle Aeroacoustic Optimization

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel adjoint-based methodology for vehicle aeroacoustic optimization. The adjoint sensitivity map on the side mirror is computed, which indicates how its geometry should change in order to reduce the wind noise transmission into the vehicle interior. The continuous adjoint method is developed for a multi-disciplinary framework used to simulate the flow-induced noise creation and transmission mechanisms: based on the incompressible flow field, noise created by the pressure fluctuations on the mirror is radiated to the side window; its vibrational response creates sound waves that propagate to the passenger compartment and contribute to the interior sound pressure level (SPL). This work focuses on the solution of the derived adjoint systems, and the computation of the sensitivity derivatives. The proposed methodology is applied to compute the sensitivity map on the side mirror of a generic vehicle model, the SAE body. The adjoint sensitivities suggest normal displacements of the geometry that would minimize the interior SPL, and are consequently a useful tool for the aeroacoustic engineers, during the vehicle development process.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Flow-induced noise that transmits into travelling road vehicles is an important factor not only for comfort, but also for safety, as it is associated to tiredness. This is why car manufacturers have invested considerable effort over the last years firstly to gain insight into aerodynamic noise creation and propagation to the interior, and secondly to develop high-fidelity numerical methods that can predict the interior noise level, without the need of a wind tunnel experiment. In this context, utilizing numerical methods for aeroacoustic optimization by means of adjoint sensitivity maps can provide useful information in the early development phase about design changes that can improve aeroacoustic performance.

Wind noise is mainly related to the exterior flow around the side mirror and the A-pillar, and dominates the cabin noise level for mid to high driving speeds. The pressure fluctuations on the mirror create noise which is radiated to all directions. A part of it meets the side window and acts as an acoustic load. Together with the strong hydrodynamic pressure, they excite the front side window to vibration, which in turn generates sound waves that propagate to the cabin and are perceived as noise by the passengers. The importance of including the acoustic part of the flow for wind noise prediction in production car applications was indicated by Hartmann¹, and one approach to calculate the radiated acoustic field from the flow sources on mirror is to use an acoustic analogy based on a fine resolved incompressible flow solution².

Adjoint methods have already been established as an efficient way to compute sensitivity derivatives with respect to a set of design variables for gradient-based shape optimization in aerodynamics. The main advantage is that the computation of adjoint sensitivities is achieved at a cost comparable to that of the numerical solution of the state equations, and practically irrespective of the number of design variables. In the continuous formulation³, the adjoint equations and sensitivity derivatives are derived by differentiating the objective function, augmented by the field and time integral of the inner product of the state equations and the adjoint variables. The adjoint equations are discretized and numerically solved to compute the adjoint fields and, through them, the sensitivity derivatives. In contrast, the discrete adjoint equations⁴ are derived directly from the discretized state equations. The method has been mostly applied to aerodynamic related optimization problems⁵⁻⁶, but recent developments focus also on aeroacoustic problems of aircraft components. Economon⁷ formulated the continuous approach for the inhomogeneous wave equation of Ffowcs Williams-Hawkins, while Zhou⁸ applied the discrete method for the permeable Ffowcs Williams-Hawkins surface approach.

In this paper the continuous adjoint method is formulated to compute the sensitivity map for vehicle aeroacoustics. Starting point is the aeroacoustic framework presented by Kabat⁹. The adjoint method is developed for the several steps of the process, described in Section 2, resulting in their corresponding adjoint systems, presented in Section 3. Through the solution of the adjoint chain, the sensitivity of the interior acoustic pressure with respect to a normal displacement of the mirror can be computed, and indicates the way the mirror shape should change, in order to improve the aeroacoustic performance of the vehicle. In Section 4, the method is applied to compute the adjoint aeroacoustic sensitivity map on the side mirror of the generic SAE vehicle.

2 WIND NOISE CREATION AND TRANSMISSION TO THE INTERIOR

The process chain developed by Kabat⁹ is used for the computational prediction of interior noise level. Based on this framework, the mathematical development of the continuous adjoint

method will be presented later. In this section, focus is laid upon the equations that govern the physical mechanisms of wind noise creation and transmission to the vehicle interior.

The incompressible flow field is computed with an IDDES simulation of the Navier-Stokes equations and the Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model. The mirror is the dominant contributor to wind noise, so only the acoustic radiation from this part is taken into consideration, computed with the Kirchhoff Integral method. The vibrational response of the window to the acoustic load is simulated by solving the bending wave equation and the acoustic propagation of the generated sound waves to the interior with the wave equation.

The aeroacoustic framework comprises the following steps:

1. Wind noise creation: Unsteady incompressible Navier-Stokes equations
2. Acoustic radiation from vehicle mirror to side window: Kirchhoff Integral
3. Window's structural vibration: Bending wave equation
4. Propagation to interior: Wave equation

The simulation of these parts results in the prediction of the acoustic field in the vehicle interior.

2.1 Wind Noise Creation

The unsteady turbulent flow field in the computational domain Ω_{ext} around the vehicle is computed by solving the 3D unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS)

$$R^p = \nabla \cdot \vec{v} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{R}^v = \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} + \nabla p = 0 \quad (2)$$

where \vec{v} is the velocity vector, p the pressure divided by the density, ν and ν_t are the bulk and turbulent viscosities, and $\mathbf{D} = (\nu + \nu_t)(\nabla \vec{u} + (\nabla \vec{u})^T)$ the stress tensor.

Regarding the modeling of turbulence, the Partial Differential Equation (PDE) of the Spalart-Allmaras (S-A) turbulence model is added to the state equations, modified based on the IDDES theory¹⁰ to act as a Sub-Grid Scale (SGS) model, when the grid in all directions is much smaller than the boundary layer thickness, and as a S-A model anywhere else.

2.2 Noise Radiation from Mirror to Window

Under the assumption that the hydrodynamic part p of the total pressure dominates the acoustic part on the mirror S_{mir} , the radiated acoustic field p' can be computed with the Kirchhoff integral method. The acoustic pressure on the surface of the side window S_{win} yields

$$R^{p'} = p' - \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{S_{mir}} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} p + \frac{1}{a_0 r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \right]_{ret} \hat{r} \cdot \hat{n} dS = 0 \quad (3)$$

Here, a_0 is the ambient speed of sound, \hat{n} the unit normal vector of the surface pointing towards the fluid, \vec{r} is the distance vector between the integration surface on the mirror and the receiver surface on the window. Moreover, the right hand side of equation 3 is expressed at the retarded time $\tau = t - \frac{r}{a_0}$, which is the time instance when a sound wave leaves the source to reach the receiver at time t .

2.3 Structural Vibration of the Window

The acoustic waves that are radiated to the side window S_{win} excite it to vibration. The lateral window displacement is governed by the two-dimensional bending wave equation,

$$R^w = \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} + \frac{D}{m'} \nabla^4 w + \eta_1 \frac{D}{m'} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla^4 w + \eta_2 \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \eta_3 \sqrt{\frac{D}{m'}} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla^2 w - \frac{p'}{m'} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where w is the window deflection, D the window bending stiffness, m' the normalized window mass, η_i the damping coefficients, and p' the acoustic pressure load. For the study that follows, the window is simply supported on its edges, thus zero Dirichlet and zero Laplacian boundary conditions are imposed for the window deflection w .

2.4 Interior Sound Propagation

The window vibration generates sound waves, which propagate into the vehicle interior. The sound radiation can be simulated by solving the wave equation in the interior computational domain Ω_{int}

$$R^{p^\alpha} = \frac{1}{a_0^2} \frac{\partial^2 p^\alpha}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 p^\alpha = 0 \quad (5)$$

On the inner side of the window S_{win} the acoustic pressure p^α is coupled with the window acceleration, and at any other interior wall S_{wa} the propagated sound waves are reflected, based on the convective velocity v_c , thus

$$\nabla p^\alpha \cdot \vec{n} = \rho_0 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \quad \text{for } \vec{x} \in S_{win} \quad (6)$$

$$\nabla p^\alpha \cdot \vec{n} = -\frac{1}{v_c} \frac{\partial p^\alpha}{\partial t} \quad \text{for } \vec{x} \in S_{wa} \quad (7)$$

2.4 An objective function for controlling interior noise

After the simulation of the above described steps, the acoustic pressure field in the vehicle interior is known. Hence it is possible for any given car and mirror geometry combination to predict the sound pressure level at any point of interest in the cabin. One approach that can be used for controlling interior noise is to minimize a measure of the total sound amplitude at a point near the driver's ear. A suitable objective function would be then mathematically expressed as the time-averaged acoustic pressure-squared at that point P

$$J = \frac{1}{T} \int_T p_P^{\alpha^2} dt \quad (8)$$

3 THE CONTINUOUS ADJOINT PROCESS FOR VEHICLE AEROACOUSTICS

During the early development phase of the mirror design, aeroacoustic engineers introduce changes to the initial geometry, in order to reduce objective functions like the one defined in eq. 8, and thus to improve the aeroacoustic performance of the vehicle. However, this is not a straight-forward task, since for broadband noise there is usually no obvious rationale behind the influence that a mirror surface deformation has on the interior noise level. A numerical method

that can indeed provide such an insight is the continuous adjoint method, which computes the sensitivity map of any objective function with respect to geometry normal displacements of the mirror.

This sensitivity map is effectively the gradient of the objective function with respect to the normal displacement of each node on the computational mesh on the mirror. It shows the optimal movement of this node in the normal direction, which will result in a decrease of the aforementioned objective function. In other words, it indicates which regions of the vehicle mirror should be pulled outward from the surface and which inwards, in order to achieve a reduction of the interior noise. The aim of this paper is to formulate the continuous adjoint method, in order to efficiently compute the aeroacoustic sensitivity map on the mirror.

Following the formulation that is described below, the adjoint fields are introduced and the continuous adjoint equations are derived. The derivation is based on the equations presented in section 2, which hereafter will be called primal equations. For each mirror design, the adjoint systems have to be solved in addition to the primal equations. The computed adjoint fields are used in the end in the expression of the sensitivity derivatives to calculate the aeroacoustic sensitivity map on the mirror.

3.1 The Continuous Adjoint Formulation

The first step of the continuous adjoint formulation is to augment the objective function with the time and space integrals of the inner product of the primal equations residuals and their corresponding adjoint variables

$$L = J + \int_T \int_{\Omega_{ext}} (\vec{u} \cdot \vec{R}^v + qR^p) d\Omega dt + \int_T \int_{S_{win}} q' R^{p'} dAdt + \int_T \int_{S_{win}} z R^w dAdt + \int_T \int_{\Omega_{int}} q^\alpha R^{p^\alpha} d\Omega dt \quad (9)$$

where \vec{u} , q , q' , z and q^α are the adjoint variables to the velocity, pressure, acoustic pressure, deflection and interior pressure respectively.

The gradient of L with respect to the design variables b_n , namely the normal displacement of each mirror surface node, reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta L}{\delta b_n} = & \frac{\delta J}{\delta b_n} + \int_T \int_{\Omega_{ext}} \left(u_i \frac{\delta R_i^v}{\delta b_n} + q \frac{\delta R^p}{\delta b_n} \right) d\Omega dt + \int_T \int_{S_{win}} q' \frac{\delta R^{p'}}{\delta b_n} dAdt \\ & + \int_T \int_{S_{win}} z \frac{\delta R^w}{\delta b_n} dAdt + \int_T \int_{\Omega_{int}} q^\alpha \frac{\delta R^{p^\alpha}}{\delta b_n} d\Omega dt \\ & + \int_T \int_{\Omega_{ext}} (\vec{u} \cdot \vec{R}^v + qR^p) \frac{\delta d\Omega}{\delta b_n} dt \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The terms including total derivatives in eq. 10 can be further expanded with the use of Gauss's theorem. This results in volume and surface integral expressions of terms involving the corresponding primal and adjoint fields, multiplied with the partial variation of the primal variables with respect to the design variables. The calculation of these partial derivatives is computationally costly and for this reason their multipliers are set to zero, deriving in this way the residuals of the continuous adjoint equations and their boundary conditions. When the adjoint equations are solved, the undesirable terms in the expression of the gradient of the objective function vanish and the remaining surface integrals on the mirror represent the sensitivity

derivatives. The interested reader is encouraged to read the complete mathematical development for the derivation of the adjoint equations and their boundary conditions in the works of Papoutsis⁶ and Kapellos¹¹.

The continuous adjoint equations draw similarities to the primal equations. An important difference is however, that the unsteady adjoint solution is integrated backwards in time. This can be explained by taking a look at the derivation of the temporal derivative of an adjoint field, for instance the adjoint velocity. Gauss's theorem on the temporal term of the Navier-Stokes equations yields

$$\int_T \int_{\Omega_{ext}} \vec{u} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial b_n} \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} d\Omega dt = \int_T \int_{\Omega_{ext}} -\frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} \cdot \frac{\delta \vec{v}}{\delta b_n} d\Omega dt + \int_{\Omega_{ext}} \vec{u} \cdot \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial b_n} d\Omega \Big|_{start}^{end} \quad (11)$$

Here, the first right hand side term will appear in the unsteady adjoint Navier-Stokes equations, whereas the second one is used to derive the initial condition of the adjoint problem. At $t = t_{start}$, the variation of the primal velocity is always zero, because the initial conditions are independent of the geometry. To avoid computing term $\partial \vec{v} / \partial b_n$ at $t = t_{end}$, the adjoint velocity \vec{u} is set to zero. Consequently, the adjoint solution has to start at the end and progresses backward in time. Similar temporal conditions are derived for all unsteady equations.

In addition to this, the adjoint information flows in reverse order. The adjoint simulation chain starts from the vehicle interior with the adjoint wave equation, followed by the adjoint deflection of the window, the adjoint Kirchhoff integral, and eventually the adjoint Navier-Stokes equations. In what follows the derived adjoint systems are presented in the order that they are simulated.

3.1 Adjoint Interior Propagation

The first step in the adjoint chain is the adjoint wave equation solved in the vehicle interior domain Ω_{int}

$$R^{q^\alpha} = \frac{1}{a_0^2} \frac{\partial^2 q^\alpha}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 q^\alpha + 2p_p^\alpha = 0 \quad (12)$$

The wave operator is self-adjoint, so the only addition to the adjoint wave equation is a source term, derived directly by the differentiation of the objective function $\delta J / \delta b_n$. This term is in fact the source of the adjoint energy in the complete system, and as shown later, acts like a monopole source in the interior, at the point near the driver's ear, where the objective function is defined.

Apart from the side window, where a zero Neumann boundary condition is imposed for the adjoint interior pressure q^α , the boundary conditions on the interior walls of the adjoint problem are the same with the primal ones. In the primal solution, the boundary condition on the side window couples the exterior domain with the interior, by imposing the interior acoustic pressure on the window as a function of the window acceleration. In the adjoint chain this coupling is realized by adding a source term in the adjoint bending wave equation and the information flows in reverse order, from the interior domain to the exterior.

3.2 Adjoint Structural Vibration of the Window

When the propagation of the adjoint interior acoustic pressure is solved, the next step is to solve the adjoint bending wave equation, which yields

$$R^z = \frac{\partial^2 z}{\partial t^2} + \frac{D}{m'} \nabla^4 z - \eta_1 \frac{D}{m'} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla^4 z - \eta_2 \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} - \eta_3 \sqrt{\frac{D}{m'} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla^2 z} - c^2 \rho \frac{\partial^2 q^\alpha}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (13)$$

As mentioned before, the source term of eq. 13 stems from the adjoint wave equation solved in the interior. The boundary conditions on the window edges, similarly to the primal ones, are a zero Dirichlet and zero Laplacian for the adjoint deflection z .

3.3 Adjoint Radiation from Window to Mirror

The derived expression for the adjoint acoustic pressure on the window yields

$$R^{q'} = q' + \frac{z}{m'} = 0 \quad (14)$$

It is clear, that the adjoint acoustic pressure is expressed on the window, so there is no information transferred yet from the side window to the mirror. This is performed when imposing the boundary condition of the adjoint velocity on the mirror, in order to solve the adjoint Navier-Stokes equations. The expression yields

$$\vec{u} = -\frac{\vec{n}}{4\pi T} \int_{S_{win}} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} q' - \frac{1}{a_0 r} \frac{\partial q'}{\partial t} \right]_{adv} (\hat{r} \cdot \hat{n}) dA \quad (15)$$

and is practically the adjoint Kirchhoff Integral, where the adjoint acoustic pressure is radiated from the side window to the mirror. Since this is done backwards in time, the quantities in the integrand of the right hand side are expressed at the advance time $\tau_{adv} = t + \frac{r}{a_0}$.

3.4 Adjoint Unsteady Flow

The last step of the adjoint aeroacoustic chain is the unsteady adjoint Navier-Stokes equations which yield

$$R^a = \nabla \cdot \vec{u} = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\vec{R}^u = -\frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} - (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{u} + \nabla \vec{v} \cdot \vec{u} - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D}^a + \nabla q = 0 \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{D}^a = (\nu + \nu_t)(\nabla \vec{u} + (\nabla \vec{u})^T)$ is the adjoint stress tensor.

The boundary condition on the mirror, eq. 15, is the source of the adjoint energy in the adjoint flow field and is the final coupling between the external and internal computational domains.

As seen in eq. 17, the adjoint velocity is convected by the primal velocity. This means that as the adjoint solution progresses backwards in time, the primal field on each time step is needed. Storing the volume velocity and pressure fields at each time step would require a great amount of memory. This is why the checkpointing technique¹² is implemented, where only a user-defined amount of time steps is stored. For the time instances that the primal solution is not available, the flow is computed again, starting from the last checkpoint.

3.4 Sensitivity Derivative Expression

After solving the four described adjoint steps, the adjoint velocity and pressure fields are known, and include the information of the sensitivity of each primal system to design changes of the mirror. These are then used in the expression of the sensitivity derivatives of the objective function with respect to the normal displacement of each boundary node on the mirror, which yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\delta J}{\delta b_n} = & - \int_T \int_{S_{mir}} (\vec{n} \cdot \mathbf{D}^a - q\vec{n}) \cdot \nabla_n \vec{v} \frac{\delta \vec{x}_n}{\delta b_n} dS dt \\
& + \int_T \int_{S_{mir}} \vec{u} \cdot \vec{n} \left(2 \vec{n} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \frac{\delta \vec{n}}{\delta b_n} + \vec{n} \cdot \nabla_n \mathbf{D} \cdot \vec{n} \frac{\delta \vec{x}_n}{\delta b_n} \right) dS dt \\
& + \frac{1}{4\pi T} \int_T \int_{S_{mir}} \int_{S_{win}} q' \left[\frac{1}{R^3} p + \frac{1}{cR^2} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \right]_{ret} (3(\hat{r} \cdot \hat{n})\hat{r} - \hat{n}) \cdot \vec{n} \frac{\delta \vec{x}_n}{\delta b_n} dA dS dt \\
& + \frac{1}{4\pi T} \int_T \int_{S_{mir}} \int_{S_{win}} q' \vec{n} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \nabla p + \frac{1}{a_0 r} \left(\frac{\partial \nabla p}{\partial t} + \frac{\hat{r}}{a_0} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2} \right) \right]_{ret} (\hat{r} \cdot \hat{n}) \frac{\delta \vec{x}_n}{\delta b_n} dA dS dt \\
& + \frac{1}{4\pi T} \int_T \int_{S_{mir}} \int_{S_{win}} q' \left(\frac{1}{r^2} p + \frac{1}{a_0 r} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \right) \hat{r} \cdot \frac{\delta(\hat{n}dS)}{\delta b_n} dA dt
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Since the equations govern unsteady phenomena, the expression in eq. 18 is also integrated in time. The first two terms indicate normal displacements of the geometry that will affect the flow field around the mirror, in a way that reduces the noise creation and propagation to the interior. The last three terms are derived from the differentiation of the Kirchhoff integral, eq. 3, and express the influence on the objective function that a change in the mirror shape will have, due to the change in the directivity of the mirror sound field.

4 IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

The proposed framework for aeroacoustic prediction and adjoint optimization is implemented in OpenFOAM[®] and was applied to the SAE fullback type 4, presented in figure 1. In this model, the noise transmission is possible only through the one side window at the driver's side. The outer shell of the geometry is used to generate the CFD computational mesh, where the velocity and pressure fields are computed. The inner cell is used for the castellated acoustic mesh, used to compute the window deflection and interior propagation.

Fig. 1 – SAE Type 4 geometry: Exterior and interior vehicle walls. The only window of the vehicle, through which sound is transmitted to the interior, is colored in magenta.

The flow simulation is performed with OpenFOAM[®] 16.12+ at a wind speed of 140 km/h. The mesh resolution near the mirror region is 1mm and a time step of 10^{-5} s is used. The convection term is discretized utilizing a blending scheme¹³ between central 2nd order at fine resolved areas and upwind scheme elsewhere.

A total of 1.3s is simulated, with a computational cost of 38h on 480 cores and the final segment of 0.3s is used for the acoustic propagation to the interior. The Kirchhoff Integral solver is implemented as an OpenFOAM[®] library and runs in parallel at a computation time of 1h on 480 cores. The window deflection and interior propagation solvers are based on OpenFOAM[®] 17.12. The finite area mesh on the window and the interior acoustic mesh have a resolution of 10mm. The time step used for the solutions of bending wave and wave equations are 10^{-7} and $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ respectively, and the time needed for the simulation is 8h on 12 cores.

The solvers for adjoint interior propagation and adjoint window deflection are also implemented in OpenFOAM[®] 17.12. The Kirchhoff Integral solver used for the sound radiation in the primal includes also the functionality for the adjoint radiation, this time from the vehicle side window to the mirror. The unsteady flow solver is based on the HELYX adjoint solver provided by ENGYS¹⁴, with in-house modifications. The primal solver settings and schemes are used for the adjoint solution and the computational cost for the adjoint bending wave and wave equations, as well as for the adjoint Kirchhoff Integral, are practically comparable. The adjoint flow solution however, requires more iterations per time step, in order to achieve a better convergence. In addition to this, the checkpointing technique is utilized to store the necessary for the adjoint solution primal flow fields, as explained in section 3. These have an effect on the total computational cost of the adjoint Navier-Stokes equations, which is around 4.8 times the flow solution.

The results of the wind noise prediction process can be seen in fig. 2. The strong hydrodynamic pressure fluctuations on the mirror create noise that radiates to all directions, and meets the side window. Its vibrational response to the acoustic load generates in turn sound waves that propagate to the cabin. After the solution of the primal chain, the adjoint equations are solved, backwards in time and in reverse order, and snapshots of the solution are presented in fig. 3. At the point near the driver's ear there is a monopole source acting, which is the input for the wave equation. The information of the variation of the objective function propagates in the vehicle interior and excites the window to adjoint vibration. The adjoint acoustic pressure on the window, connected to its adjoint deflection, is radiated from the side window to the vehicle mirror, where it contributes to the boundary condition of the adjoint velocity. The latter flows in the external computational domain through the boundary condition on the mirror and is convected backwards in time by the primal velocity field. In the end of the simulation, the aeroacoustic adjoint sensitivity map is computed, as seen in fig. 4; it indicates the optimal normal direction in which the mirror geometry should be deformed, in order to achieve a reduction of the wind noise transmitted to the driver's ear and thus improve the aeroacoustic performance of the vehicle

6 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, the continuous adjoint formulation was developed for an existing multi-disciplinary framework for wind noise prediction in vehicles. This includes an unsteady IDDES flow simulation to compute the hydrodynamic pressure on the mirror, the main noise source that is investigated, the Kirchhoff Integral formulation to extract and radiate the acoustic components from the mirror to the vehicle side window, a structural vibration simulation to compute the

window vibration and the interior propagation simulation, to compute the interior acoustic pressure field.

The continuous adjoint method was developed for all the aforementioned equations, and the corresponding adjoint systems were derived. After the solution of the primal and adjoint process chains, it is possible to obtain the aeroacoustic adjoint sensitivity map on the mirror. It takes into consideration the physics of all noise creation and transmission mechanisms, and it provides guidance to the aeroacoustic engineer for the optimal normal deformation of the mirror that will improve the aeroacoustic performance of the vehicle.

It is practically the first time that the continuous adjoint method is applied to a multi-disciplinary industrial problem of high complexity. The aeroacoustic sensitivity map offers an alternative for engineers to gain insight into vehicle aeroacoustics, and it can also be used in an optimization loop, in order to iteratively find the optimal mirror shape with regard to the interior sound pressure level.

However, it must be pointed out, that the computational cost of the method remains an issue to be addressed. Although the storage of the primal field is reduced by using the checkpointing technique, there is still a trade-off between memory needs and computation time, which is not easy to alleviate. On the other hand, advances in the stability of the unsteady adjoint Navier-Stokes equations will definitely reduce the required time for their solution. Moreover, the implementation of an objective function in frequency domain could also be advantageous for an aeroacoustic investigation.

Fig. 2 – Snapshots of the wind noise prediction chain: On the left, the solution in the exterior domain is presented. The flow in the region of focus is described by the A-pillar and mirror vortices, here shown by the iso-surface of Q criterion (magenta). The hydrodynamic pressure fluctuations on the mirror radiate sound waves to all directions, which also reach the side window. On the right, the vibrational response of the window is depicted. The acceleration generates sound waves that propagate to the interior and are perceived as noise.

Fig.3 – Snapshots of the continuous adjoint chain in the interior: The adjoint wave equation is solved first in the interior and the source term is a monopole at the position where the objective function is defined, here at the red dot near the driver’s ear (left). After the adjoint solution propagated into the interior, it reaches the side window and excites it to adjoint vibration (right).

Fig.4 – The continuous adjoint method for shape optimization in vehicle aeroacoustics: Minimizing the wind noise propagated to the interior of the SAE vehicle, near the driver's ear (red dot, left). The continuous adjoint sensitivity map on the mirror indicates how its geometry should change in order to reduce the interior noise. Blue areas must be pulled outward from the surface, while red areas must be pushed inward.

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